

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18344093

Organised Criminal Groups Activities In Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The history of the underworld and of organized crime is much less opaque. Charting the early roots of modern organised crime, over the years, researchers in the field of crime as done a great deal to exposed the difficulty that surrounded the study of organised crime by exposing their modus operandi across board, which exposes their activities for further researches in the field of criminology. It is in the above light that this paper uses mainly secondary data to examine the activities of three (3) organised criminal groups in Nasarawa State and Nigeria at large, namely Banditry, Boko Haram and Fulani militia group. At the end of the study, it was discovered that organised criminal groups activities in the study area constitute; kidnapping, arson, cattle rustling, looting, raping, killings, destruction of life and properties, displacement of people from their community, imposition of tax on local community among others. Due to the high rate of organised criminal groups' activities in Nasarawa State and Nigeria at large, the study recommended that the ugly trait need urgent attention. Government should address the root factors that give birth to organised criminal groups, government should beef up security to control the activities of organised criminal groups., traditional institutions and stakeholders should dialogue with organised criminal groups to prevent the impact on the people, the welfare of citizens should be taken seriously, government should provide job opportunity for the teeming youths to discourage them from forming and joining organised criminal groups, politician should stop hiring youths to use them as thugs for their selfish gain in the society.

Keywords, organised crime, organized criminal group, activities.

INTRODUCTION

The history of the underworld and of organized crime is much less opaque. Charting the early roots of modern organised crime, Mary McIntosh was one of the earliest theorists of organised crime to attempt to historicize the underworld, its hierarchies and practices. McIntosh (1975), like many historians and criminologists since, looked back to the role of bandit, brigands, and outlaws in early modern peasant society, an approach shaped by the work of Eric Hobsbawm (1969), seminal text on Bandits, published in the late 1960s, attempted to explain the role of separate societies or counter-societies that emerged as a means of protecting local interests against the authorities (the gentry, clergy, or state) (Hobsbawm 1969), stated that the bandit was faced with a choice and had to decide whether to become a criminal or a revolutionary. Thus the two could not coexist: "The underworld (as its name implies) is an anti-society, which exists by reversing the values of the straight world. It is in its own phrase, 'bent' but is otherwise parasitic on it" (Hobsbawm, 1969) In an earlier book had characterized the Mafia as developing from the antipathy to feudalism in rural Italy (Hobsbawm, 1959).

More recently, from 2003-2006 accounts of the development of groups such as the Sicilian Mafia have been much more nuanced. In the useful summary Howard Abadinsky describes the evolution of four Italian criminal organizations: the Sicilian Mafia, the Neapolitan Camorra, the 'Ndrangheta "Brotherhood" of Calabria, and the Sacra Corona Unita of the Puglia region (Abadinsky, 2003). The most well known of these, the Mafia and the Camorra, had very different roots, according to Abadinsky (2003), argued that the Mafia developed from the emergence of middlemen called Gabelotti, who ruled over the estates that had previously been controlled by the aristocracy. This aristocracy had increasingly come under attack during the nineteenth century, and ultimately, the land was freed through the campaigns of Giuseppe Garibaldi (Abadinsky 2003).

As Alan Wright notes, "the collapse of the feudal system after the rise and fall of Napoleon in the early nineteenth century marked the emergence of the Mafia into a *società* (society) of families that mediated between the landowners and the masses" (Wright, 2006). The Camorra, according to Abadinsky, (2003) was deliberately structured as a secret society and was more organised and disciplined than the Mafia. In other European countries, organizations or groups with similar profiles to the Italian societies are likely to have existed. In Germany there was increasing reference to societies or gangs of crooks from the eighteenth century on. Katrin Lange has stressed that the contemporary debates about such gangs were vague and often arbitrary, allowing the authorities to target offenders variously labeled as beggars, tramps, gypsies, cheats, robbers, and bandits, or using the term *Gauner* (crooks) (Lange, 2004).

Küther, 1976 argues that the problem of gangs and bandits was one of poor control. The eighteenth-century judicial system was not well equipped to deal with the sub-cultural nature of such groups, he argues, the state failed to deal effectively with them. To some extent this may have been due to the lack of unification in German territories that left borders permeable and law enforcement structures far from centralized. Arguably, it was only after the Napoleonic wars and the adoption of the Napoleonic Code in some parts of Germany (such as the regions of the west bank of the Rhine and the Grand Duchy of Baden), that the judicial system was to become more effective (Lindström 2004,).

Egmond, 1993 has researched organised crime in the Netherlands, focusing on various marginal groups in the early modern Dutch republic. Egmond's particularly notes the role of ethnic groups such as Jews and gypsies, as well as their links with organised crime by the late eighteenth century and the rise of vagrancy and dearth from the 1740s (Egmond 1993).

Similarly, Danker's studies of gangs of robbers in eighteenth century Coburg found that the gangs there included a significant number of Jewish vagrants (Danker's, 2001). On the other hand, Danker also found groups that were made up of farmers and artisans from the local area. While the eighteenth century seems to have been crucial in the Dutch and German examples, Egmond, (1993), suggests that it would be unwise to impose any neat chronology onto the development of organised crime in the Netherlands: "To put it briefly: Organised rural crime did not become more (or less) professional in the period 1650-1800".

Evans's discussion of the underworld in nineteenth century Germany demonstrates how "criminal careers" unraveled and the ways in which German commentators increasingly portrayed such individuals as members of an organised criminal underworld (Evans, 1998). Here Evans draws attention to the important role of the social commentators and reformers of the nineteenth century, who would use the burgeoning print culture of newspapers, periodicals, pamphlets, and books to "discover" the underworld. Moreover, while many of the accounts of gangs in continental Europe stress the disorganised, marginal, and fluid nature of the groups, it may be that in nineteenth century Europe, the underworld become more anchored to growing urban spaces. In Britain the relationship between print culture and representations of organised crime flourished in the early to mid-eighteenth century.

Howson, (1970). Wild's activities in controlling crime in early eighteenth century London, and his collusion with the authorities, have been well documented. Perhaps in common with some of the later European incarnations of organised crime,

Wild, (1750), was notable for seizing opportunities created by the authorities. In this case, the rise of a statutory award system from the 1690s facilitated the creation of a significant crime culture in the early eighteenth century (Beattie, 2001). Other historians of the eighteenth century metropolis have drawn

attention to criminal gangs and networks that seem to have come into being at least in part as a result of “moral panics” Ward, (2014).

The extent to which any pervasive organised crime networks actually existed in eighteenth century Britain is debatable. Once illegal markets are accessed for the disposal of stolen goods, such criminal activity becomes inherently organised. However, it would take the modernizing aspects of society for more recognizable models of organised crime to evolve; the creation and circulation of financial instruments, new technologies in firearms, safes and transport infrastructures; the development of a strong surveillance culture that legislated the “habitual criminal” into being; the growth of global networks via colonialism; and the creation of the “underworld” in texts and literatures that could be accessed by a wide range of readers Shore, (2015).

A history of Nigeria organised crime is an astoundingly ambitious piece of work provided by Ellis’s, (2015). The author offered an account of the history of “organised crime” in Nigeria based on the empirical research. According to the author, from the beginning of the country, it was obvious that Nigeria could present conditions comfortable for the organised crime. He observed that on account of presentation endemic corruption that lack of nationalism and ethnic division was making politics a game for personal gain. According to the author, by early 1960s, politicians were involved in business in one way or another and had started to enthrone corruption in the place of business ethics. The entrenchment of corruption but subsequent military regime provides the need material foundation for organised criminality to thrive. Nigerian organised crime from the 1980s onward has been promoted by lack of sound leadership and politics of corruption. The perpetration of tribalism and religion created room for emergence of home breed terrorism and proliferation arms, small and light weapons as well as drugs are needed in the operation of organised criminals. It is in this context, that Ellis, (2015), observed the emergence of different type of organised crime group in Nigeria including the drug trade, a business context in which perceived or real qualities that Nigerians possess are sought after; advanced fee scams also known as “419” frauds after the section of the Nigerian penal code addressing fraud, that Nigerians are often identified with internationally; sex trafficking; and oil fraud and smuggling involving the participation of significant “upper world” figures including senior government officials. Ellis,(2015).

There are several types of organised criminal activities and operatives in West Africa. These activities include drug trafficking, advanced fee and internet fraud, human trafficking, diamond smuggling, forgery, cigarette smuggling, money laundering, arms manufacture, arm trafficking, and arm robbery as well as oil bunkering. These organised criminals are not only national but also transnational organised criminals. Their activities often involve collaboration among local and foreign criminal groups. They can infiltrate governments, businesses, political and economic system. Their focus is to undermine the effectiveness of the socio political system through corruption, use of deceptive means and violence.

In 21 century in West Africa, organised criminal group have involved the manipulation of religion to their advantage. For instance the Boko Haram militant groups and the Islamic State for West Africa Province. (ISWAP) have manipulated the tenet of Islamic religion to emerge as militant criminals groups.

Nigeria has been plaque by a number of insecurity issues, arising from different militia groups these include the militant groups formed in the Niger- Delta region to protest exploitation and environmental degradation due to oil exploration, the Boko Haram insurgency in the North Eastern part of the country, the Fulani militia group that is spread like wild fire across the country to mention but few. All these have been posing a variety of security threats to the country.

Officers of the Federal Capital Territory Police Command attached to the State Criminal Investigation Department have arrested 11 suspected armed robbers wrecking havoc on residents in the nation’s capital city, Abuja and Nasarawa State, Parading the suspects on Friday, the Commissioner of Police, FCT Command, Sadiq Abubakar, revealed that they were arrested a few kilometres from Abuja at You and You Hotel in the Masaka area of Nasarawa State. The suspects arrested on December 22, 2022. Exhibits recovered from the gang include five AK 47 rifles, four G-3 rifles, 122 live ammunitions of 7.62MM, one locally made pistol without ammunition, three ballistic vests, six AK 47 empty magazines and seven G-3 empty magazines. Other exhibits include charms of various degree, one police sgt warrant card, one vigilante ID card, one Civil Defence ID card, a Toyota Camry 2000 model, golden colour with

registration number GGE 702 CH, one Gold-3 wagon, green colour with registration number KWL 22 GQX, two generators and one filing machine. (Punch, 30th December, 2022).

Police in Nasarawa State paraded 30 suspected criminals who were arrested for various offences including kidnapping, armed robbery and cultism among other crimes across the state. The command's spokesman, DSP Ramhan Nansel, told newsmen that 15 suspects were arrested for kidnapping, two for armed robbery, and four for cultism while nine were nabbed for other crimes. (Sun, October 2nd 2023).

No state in the country is immune from the activities of organised criminal gang. For instance, Zamfara State has become a centre of Bandits in the North western region, while kidnapping which started in the south-south region is now widely practiced in the Northern States of Niger and Kaduna. Nasarawa State is having her fair share of organised criminal activities.

The paper attempted to examine the activities of organised criminal groups in Nasarawa state, Nigeria.

Conceptual clarifications

Activities: this refer to a wide range of things people do, it can be hobbies, sport and fitness, social activities, educational activities, and so on and so forth. In the content of this paper activities mean the criminal act perpetrated by organised criminal groups in the society.

Organised Crime: This is a criminal activity that are planned and controlled by powerful groups and carried out on a large scale. It is a category of transnational, national, or local groupings of highly centralized enterprises run by criminals to engage in illegal activity, most commonly for profit.

Organised Criminal Group: Means a group that would likely encourage its members, including members of its sub-group to collectively or frequently engage in violent illegal act. They operate in well organised transnational, national or local groups and cooperate to carry out coordinated illegal action. The groups typically involve certain hierarchies and are headed by one or several powerful leader(s).

There are so many types of organised criminal groups in Nigeria namely: Banditry, Boko Haram, Fulani herdsmen militia, Niger Delta Militants, cult groups, cyber crime group, trafficking groups, pirates and oil bunkering, political thugs and so on and so forth.

However, the groups consider in this paper are Banditry; Boko Haram and Fulani Militia.

Banditry

Conceptually, banditry is a derivative of the term bandit meaning an unlawful armed group terrorizing people and confiscating their properties. It is synonymous with the establishment of gang groups who use small and light weapons to carry out attacks against people. In this regard, banditry could mean a set-up criminal activity deliberately designed and carried out for personal gains. Due to the complex nature of bandits' activities, Egwu (2016) in a restricted manner, described banditry as a practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders or raiding of cattle from their ranches.

Boko Haram

'Boko Haram is derived from a combination of two words, "Boko" and "Haram" The word "Boko" Is a native Hausa word, originally meaning sham, fraud, in authenticity, and such which came to represent Western education and learning. (Liman, 1968). Hence, 'Boko' came to symbolize Western education or Westernization, while 'Haram', according to the Merriam-Webster dictionary is an Arabic word which means 'forbidden', 'ungodly' or 'sinful'. Put together, the term, "Boko Haram" literally translates thus, 'Westernization is sinful', 'Western education is forbidden' or 'Western influence is a sin'. Barna (2014) noted that Boko Haram is the name commonly associated with the organization 'Jama'atu Ahlis-sunnah Lidda'Awati Wa'l-Jihad', or 'the people committed to the propagation of the prophet's teachings and Jihad'.

Fulani militia

The Fulani militia comes from a nomadic, predominantly tribe. In 2014 the militia group was named the fourth deadliest terrorist group in the world by the Global Terrorism Index. The Fulani herdsmen militia is a pastoralist ethnic group living in the central regions of Nigeria, predominantly in the middle belt. The militias group has clashed with indigenous tribes and local, mainly over grazing land.

While, there is no general acceptable definition of Fulani militia group, however, this study define the group as the socio cultural ethnic group that organised to perpetrate crime in the name of grazing across Nigeria society.

Factors Responsible for Organised Criminal Group's Formation in Nigeria

Organised criminal groups in Nigeria before 1990s was not pronounced are rarely mentioned in the trend of crime. Obarisiagbon and Aderinto, (2018). However, the current trend of organised criminal groups' activities in Nigeria could be trace to February, 25, 2000 with the abduction of oil company employee in the Niger Delta region to express their grievances, exploitation and underdevelopment Akpan in Yusuf and Abdullahi, (2020).

Nigeria organised crime is an astoundingly ambitious piece of work provided by Ellis's (1953-2015).The author offered an account of the history of "organised crime" in Nigeria based on the empirical research. According to him, from the beginning of the country, it was obvious that Nigeria could present conditions comfortable for the organised crime. He observed that on account of presentation endemic corruption that lack of nationalism and ethnic division was making politic a game for personal gain. According to him, by early 1960s, politicians were involved in business in one way or another and had started to enthrone corruption in the place of business ethics. The entrenchment of corruption but subsequent military regime provides the need material foundation for organised criminality to strive. Nigerian organised crime from the 1980s onward has been promoted by lack of sound leadership and politics of corruption. The perpetration of tribalism and religion created room for emergence of home breed terrorism and proliferation arms, small and light weapons as well as drugs are needed in the operation of organised criminals. Ellis (2015), base on the above statements, the factors that led to the formation of organised criminal groups in Nigeria was extracted from the works of Ellis, (1953-2015), summarily, to includes; lack of nationalism, ethnic division, politics of corruption, personal gain, proliferation of small arm and light weapons, lack of sound leadership and drugs abuse. Ellis, (2015).

Structure of Nigerian organised criminal groups

An analysis of literature on Nigerian criminality worldwide revealed that the main characteristic emphasized is its great flexibility and ability to adapt to the national context in which it is operating. Whether it is some countries of the European Union, USA or generically foreign countries, Nigerian criminal groups seem to be based on loose and fluid organizations rather than hierarchical structures. According to the Europol, (2011), report on trafficking in human beings, Nigerian criminal groups are highly flexible in nature; they conduct operations in cells active in several EU member States, transferring victims easily from one country to another (Europol, 2011, p.26).

In this regards, Phil Williams claims that many Nigerian criminal organizations are relatively small, and are based around bonds created by family membership, tribal affinity, or personal friendship. Often these groups operate within a larger network that resembles trade association rather than traditional mafia hierarchies. The fluid network provides support, structure, and potential connections that can be activated when it is convenient or beneficial to those involved (Williams, 2014).

Following a similar interpretative line, Stephen Ellis, (2015). Points out like legitimate businessmen, they conduct themselves as independent small traders, using family connections scattered around the globe to pursue criminal enterprise.

Nigerian law-breakers are also involved in organised criminality. Their involvement is seen as lose and fluid alliances driven by specific criminal objective through the associations always remain and can be drawn upon at any time, the actual work of completing a specific criminal project leads to the development of temporary relationships to complete the project at hand. Thereafter, the business alliances often dissolve as each criminal task is completed for the most part; Nigerian criminals remain opportunists par excellence. Their flexibility is a big part of their success. Ellis, (2015).

The interpretation of the Nigerian criminality above points out the existence of small loose organised groups. It seems that at times Nigerian criminal players share ad hoc criminal projects. When the criminal goal is accomplished, the alliance network could end leaving each criminal player to establish new relationships with other groups. In addition, Nigerian criminal groups have 'ethnic' ties related to the family, clan, or the shared cultural background/nationality. For criminal players to relying on some extra

resources such as ethnic or other kind of bounds, means compensating for a structural problem of trust regarding illegal markets Smith, (1980).

Nigerian criminal groups have been able to spread worldwide: according to Williams, (2014). They are present in 60 countries Williams, (2014). For instance, in Italy, the initial research on Nigerian criminal groups dates back to early 2000. Some researches depict them as horizontal and no vertical groups when it comes to generically organised crime rather than mafia associations specifically because they would not have the capability to threaten or intimidate people in the Italian social environment where they are settled , Gustincich, (2005, p,221).

At the same time, a report by the Anti-Mafia Investigation Directorate Dia, (2001) described the national scenario of Nigerian criminal groups. Mainly focusing on drug trafficking and sexual exploitation, from the recruitment of victims to exploitation in Italy by the so-called mamas, the institutional report provides little knowledge about forms of organizations limited to drug trafficking. Nigerian criminal groups generically present a severe characterization based on the tribal origins of their members. They have a vertical structure in which the one or two strictly Nigerian criminal leaders emerged. These leaders manage the international drug trafficking and do not have contact with floor members, the drug couriers.

More recently, a report by the Italian Ministry of Interior (2017) claimed that Nigerian criminal groups acting in Italy have the capability to manage, even at the same time, a variety of illegal sectors, and parceling out of operative cellules as well, which do not constitute a solely hierarchical association but rather a wider intercontinental network in which local criminal groups, despite sharing greater transnational designs, operate autonomously. In these terms, the report points out the versatility, flexibility and autonomy of Nigerian criminal groups acting in Italy. A recent report endorsed by the Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs pointed out the mafia type characteristics of Nigerian criminal groups. The latter are based on secrecy, unity, an oligarchic structure, initial rituals, familism or tribalism/clannism and territorial control (Di Liddo *et al.*, 2019, 15)

Organised criminal groups activities

Since the early 1980s, Nigeria has recorded several types of organised criminal activities. Many of these activities persist in spite of the efforts of successive governments to combat them with support from foreign governments and agencies. The common types of trans-border and domestic criminal activities by groups and networks are drug trafficking, money laundering, corruption and fraud, trafficking in persons especially women and children, smuggling of firearms, kidnapping and armed robbery, oil theft, and piracy (Ikoh, 2013). Organised criminal groups become transnational when they move persons, goods and services across sovereign national borders in a manner devoid of acceptable norms and standards (Ikoh, 2013). Nigerian citizens have been arrested for drug trafficking in many countries. A report by the United States International Narcotics and Law Enforcement Affairs (US-INLEA) observes that Nigerian criminal enterprises are organised and active in at least 60 countries around the world. They launder money in Hong Kong, buy cocaine in the Andes, run prostitution and gamble rings in Spain, and corrupt legitimate businesses in Great Britain with their financial crime (US-INLEA, 2013).

The activities of bandits include; kidnapping, arson, cattle rustling, looting, raping, killings among others Akinyetun, (2022). The Wave of kidnapping activities in Nigeria has started to attract attentions beginning from the well reported kidnapped and abduction of an expatriate oil worker in the oil rich region of the Niger Delta around 25thFebruary, 2006 Ibrahim & Ahmad, (2020). Activities of three different groups were found to constitute organised criminal groups activities in Nasarawa State. These include: Banditry, Boko Haram and Fulani militia activities. It was discovered that their activities include assault, rape, robbery, theft at farms, mounting of road blocks, extortion of money, kidnapping, drugs sale and arms sale. Phd. Thesis submitted to department of sociology, Federal University Lafia, (2025).

However, the menace of armed-banditry and kidnapping has recently become reoccurring incidences threaten the peace and survival of people living especially in the North-West states of Nigeria Akinyetun, (2022). It has become an order of the day and no longer attract the attention it deserves from the National and international governments, institutions and organizations. Only few cases hit the headlines of the National Dailies, even though it occurs on a daily basis and seems to defy all possible remedies. People are harassed, rape, kidnapped, killed and their properties are destroyed, homes are set ablaze by mostly

Fulani herders (also known as Bandits) and few other miscreants Bashir & Mustapha, (2022, March). Presently, there is no issue bothering most states in the North West Nigeria than the problem of armed banditry and kidnapping. People no longer sleep with their two eyes closed; as a result many communities are now homeless, restless, despair, helpless and pathetic. Life per se in many places and areas has become more uncertain, terrible and almost similar to what was obtained or known during the state of nature as described by John Locke (1632-1704).

In the Northern States banditry and kidnapping is rampant in states such as Zamfara, Katsina, Sokoto, Niger, Kaduna, Kebbi, Abuja and Kogi. The kidnapping groups usually operate both in the rural and urban areas in Northern Nigeria, and often demand for high ransom payment from the families of the victims, and consequently leave the families and victims financially bankrupt, in many instances bandits enforce levies to many communities in the rural areas Adetayo, (2022). It has since become easiest and lucrative business to the gang of criminals, fuelling and aiding this devilish act is the lackadaisical attitude on the part of security agencies, activities of informants and saboteurs. The incidence continues to escalate between 2017 and 2018. Recently some local governments in Katsina State have become the soft target due to their closeness to thick and vast forests spread across Zamfara, Kaduna and Niger States. These vast forests serve as a shelter to those carryout the notorious, nefarious and devilish acts, it was reported that hundreds of bandits infest the vast Rugu Forest of Katsina State and turned it as the safest place to invade villages and kidnap people Daily Trust, (2021, 16).

Reports indicate the flourishing of bandit groups, whose members were seen displaying automatic weapons, terrorizing herders' settlements, farms, villages and the highways with the mission of killing people, kidnapping and pillaging cows Olaniyan, (2018). It was reported that between October, 2013 and March, 2014, 7,000 cattle were rustled from commercial livestock farms and traditional herders in Northern Nigeria Bashir, (2014; Tauna, (2016) while about 330 attacks were made by bandits and 1,460 deaths were recorded between January and July, 2019 Abdullahi, (2019). In most cases, the bandits killed and maimed the people and raped the women before dispossessing them of their cows Akowe & Kayode, (2014) while in some instances, they also kidnapped girls or women in the process Adeniyi, & Yusuf, (2015).

It is however, pertinent to note that the incidences of organised criminal activities are not limited to northwestern Nigeria alone. In fact, it is also prevalent in some parts of north-central region, in states like Niger, Nasarawa, Benue and Plateau which are equally regarded as hotbeds Kuna & Jibrin (2016). No state in the country is immune from the activities of organised criminal gang. For instance, Zamfara State has become a centre of Bandits in the North western region, while kidnapping which started in the south-south region is now widely practiced in the Northern States of Niger and Kaduna. Nasarawa State is having her fair share of organised criminal activities. The increasing attacks of bandit groups have led to the destruction of lives and properties, displacement of people from their communities; and a growing numbers of widows; widowers and orphans, who now reside in Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) camps following the continued attacks of armed bandits on both farming and pastoral communities across different areas of the states (Okoli & Ochim, 2016; Mustapha, 2019).

The Boko Haram and ISWAP that have operated through stealing, looting of stores of local farmers and villages as well as robbing banks and businesses organizations especially in the North Eastern part of Nigeria, are relocating to Nasarawa State due to successful destabilization of their base in Sambisa forest by the Military. The group is fast regrouping and infiltrating into the local population. It is providing governance at fringes and forest borders between Nasarawa State and Benue State, Nasarawa State and Taraba State; and Nasarawa State and FCT, Abuja. It is creating illegal routes and link for arms and drugs trafficking contrary to official claims therefore that Boko Haram terrorists have been restricted to the North-East part of Nigeria, the group is said to have successfully infiltrated into Nasarawa State, North central Nigeria, and has been carrying on several attacks in the State. While briefing President Buhari on Boko Haram infiltration into Nasarawa State, the State Governor, Engr. Abdulahi Sule, observed that "members of the Boko Haram have relocate to a place called Utu in Toto Local Government Area" and that in attempt by the special Task Force to dislodge them, nine hundred (900) members of the group members were captured including children and wives Ayitogo, (2021). In the findings of Attah, (2021),

the Boko Haram terrorist group is living in Nasarawa State as organised criminal group and is using Nasarawa as a base to attack their targets and also exploit the local economy. The terrorist group is regrouping in communities that cut across four local Government Areas of Nasarawa State. These include Karu, Wamba, Nasarawa Toto and Awe. These Local Government Areas share boundaries and Localities with the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Kaduna, Plateau, Benue and Taraba States.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Frustration aggression theory

The frustration aggression theory is a theory that emphasis on aggression. Proponent of this theory includes John Dollard and Neal E. Miller (1939) and Leonard Berkowitz in 1969. The theory states that aggression is the result of blocking or frustrating a person's effort to attain a goal. The theory hypothesized that aggression is always the result of frustration. According to the proponents, frustration produces instigations to a number of different types of responses, one of which is instigation to some of aggression. Discussing further on the postulation, Anifowose (2003, p.48) submitted that, given the requisite conditions, individuals or groups who feel frustrated in the attainment of their desire and demands often react by directing aggressive behavior at what is perceived as being responsible for depriving those desire, as a substitute.

It could be argued from the above standpoint that the emergence of the Boko Haram , Fulani Militia organised criminal group in northeast of Nigeria and banditry in other parts of Nigeria, Nasarawa state inclusive could have resulted partly because of the inability of the Nigeria government to meet the need of its citizens. Provision of basic needs, poverty eradication, and employment opportunities could have help reduce the incessant formation of organised criminal groups that have gripped the country in recent year. This is because as Anifowose (1982) posited; when groups feel alienated and there is further feeling that such alienation is entrenched, it could degenerate into formation of violent militia group as the groups increasingly resort to desperate measure to break the yolk.

This state of deprivation and social injustice may have driven groups to form organised criminal groups and to take up arms against the state to break the yolk as a counter measure to address their grievances.

This was the case with the emergence of Boko Haram organized criminal group in Maduguri, Borno state. Aliyu, Moorthy and Idris (2015) reported that in the years between 2000-2003, the sect supported the gubernatorial candidature and actively contributed to the electoral victory of Senator Ali Modu Sheriff owing to the east while government seems resistance under the leadership of Mala Kachalla towards total implementation of Sharia in the State. Walker (2012) noted this point as the watershed in the sect's existence, morphing into a State within a State. Hence, Pham (2013) highlighted the defiance of the group towards the Nigerian State and its seemingly emboldened nature during the government of Governor Sheriff in Borno State. Thus, their ideology spread across the Northeastern States of Borno, Yobe, Bauchi, Gombe and other States in Northern Nigeria viz Niger, Nasarawa, Kano, and Kaduna.

When the governments of Borno under Ali Modu Sherif resisted the group to practice sharia law in the state, the group turns against the government of the day. When they were frustrated by the government, the group ostracized and begins to mob out strategies to fight back the government. As observed by Soyinka (2014), Boko Haram has a very long history; whether described as an army of the discontent or as marginalized or feeling marginalized, the movement relies on religion as a fuel for their operation, mobilization, and augmentation of any other legitimate or illegitimate grievance that they might have against society.

CONCLUSION

The rising rate of organised criminal groups activities in Nasarawa state and Nigeria at large is a source of worried and call for urgent concern. People had physical, social, psychological and economic impact as results of organised criminal groups' activities in the country. Ajibola, (2015) who asserts that the Boko Haram insurgency has had physical, social, psychological and economic impact on women and children in Northeast Nigeria including physical attacks, abductions, bomb blasts, kidnappings, destruction of property, attacks and destruction of schools etc. killing thousands of students and their teachers; adversely

affecting school enrolment and attendance as parents restrict their wards from school for fear of terror attacks. The group is said to have successfully infiltrated into Nasarawa State, North central Nigeria, and has been carrying on several attacks in the State.

However, due to the high rate of organised criminal groups' activities in Nigeria today, Nasarawa state inclusive. The paper recommended that the ugly trait need urgent attention. Government should address the root factors that give birth to organised criminal groups, government should beef up security to control the activities of organised criminal groups., traditional institutions and stakeholders should dialogue with organised criminal groups to prevent the impact on the people, the welfare of citizens should be taken seriously to discourage people from forming and joining organised criminal groups, politician should stop hiring youths to use them as thugs for their selfish gain in the society.

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